

Saussurea obvallata (Brahma's Lotus) –An updated review

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Abstract— *Saussurea obvallata* is a traditional herbal plant for its considerable medicinal properties. It is one of the richest natural sources of health benefits for humans and animals. To increase the understanding of the cultural significance, medicinal uses and safety against health risks of *S. obvallata*. Different plant parts of *S. obvallata* are used in traditional medicine for the treatment of cerebral palsy, stroke, sexual disorders, pulmonary infections, urinary tract infections, and evaluation of phytochemicals, antioxidant antimicrobial and anti-cancer activities. The information presented here may be useful for researchers, healthcare professionals and pharmaceutical companies to design and develop effective drugs against microorganisms, antimicrobial, anti-cancer activities.

Keywords— *Saussurea obvallata*, Himalayan King, Brahma kamal, Antioxidant, Traditional medicine

I. INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicines have been used in conventional Indian system and other medical systems around the world since ancient times owing to their low cost, efficacy and few or no side effects. These attributes, known as “natural” medicines, are increasingly attracting the attention of the world’s population. A World Health Organization (WHO) survey has shown that 80% of the population in developing countries still relies on traditional and folk medicine, 85% of traditional medicines are prepared from plant extracts, and nearly 70% of prescribed human medicines are derived from plants [1-3]. The international market for herbal medicines is estimated to be around US\$ 62 billion, which is set to grow to US\$ 5 trillion by 2050 in the Asian and international markets [4]. The demand for herbal medicines in India is estimated to be US\$ 1 billion per year [5], and Himalayn mountain (Utterkand) is one of the richest sources of various medicinal plants.

Saussurea is a very important genus of the Asteraceae family for various reasons, and most of the species in this genus are well studied internationally [6–9]. It is commonly known as Brahma Kamal and is the state flower of Uttarakhand (India). It is a well-known plant throughout Uttarakhand for its traditional, ornamental, medicinal and religious purposes [10]. It is used to treat different diseases or disorders such as cerebral ischemia, stroke, wounds, mental disorders and heart disorders; some people use it as an antiseptic and to heal cuts etc. [10]. Starting investigations on the phytochemicals found in *S. obvallata* (standard) were conducted by Semwal et al. [11] and its phytochemical composition was reported by Mishra et al. [12]. The present review article has demonstrated that anti-oxidant, antimicrobial, anti-cancer activity, phytoconstituents, traditional medicinal uses of *S. obvallata* leaves and flowers (whole plant) have been carry out to identify the active components.

Environment adaptation of *Saussurea obvallata*

The Indian Himalayan region, which incorporates the Himalayas and adjacent mountain ranges in the northern part of India, is especially delicate and exposed mountain ecology. Winter and summer are the two prime seasons. Summers are short and cool; winters are long and bitterly cold. Depending on the altitude, the alpine climate varies. As the altitude changes, it becomes colder and drier, and as it becomes wetter. The Indian Himalayan regions experience rapid fluctuations in weather and temperature. Snowfall usually occurs throughout the year in high alpine areas. Monsoons, floods, strong winds, snowstorms and other variety of precipitation can occur suddenly, making the climate here calm, unstable and unpredictable [13]. Moreover, the air is very dry, thin, and rainfall amounts are relatively low at higher altitudes. The Eastern Himalayas and the Western Himalayas, two subgroups of the region, are recognized as various plant geographical zones. More than 50% of Indian flora or about 10,000 species of vascular plants are found in the Indian Himalayas. But most of the high-alpine ecosystems in the Indian Himalayas

are rocky deserts with year-round snow and harsh conditions. As a result, only a little species of vascular plants can survive here. They have to adapt to the harsh conditions, strong winds, and short growing season. The tall species of the genus *Saussurea* discussed here are all dwarf, growing low to the ground and measuring 5 to 10 cm tall. They form a thick basal rosette of leaves, and the Eastern Himalayas and Western Himalayas, two subgroups of the region, are recognized as various phytogeographic zones. The flowering stem is roughly spiral. The flowers grow in a dense head of small capitula which are inconspicuous hairs. The ample woolly hairs protect the flowers from UV rays from harsh high sunlight and aid in thermoregulation by reducing frost damage at night.

Other names of *Saussurea obvallata*

Local names include Hindi, Sanskrit and Nepal. Khas Chhetri, from the far west of Nepal, English.

English: King of Himalayan, Sacred *Saussurea*, Flowers, Brahma's Lotus.

Hindi: Brahma Kamal, Bhramha Phool, Dev Pushp,

Marathi: Brahma kamad

Nepal: Khas Chhetri.

Tamil Name: Bramma Kamalam.

Distribution of *Saussurea obvallata*

It grows in the Himalayan region at an altitude of 3000-4800 m in India, Tibet, Nepal, Pakistan, China, Bhutan and Myanmar. It can be found in the Himalayan alpine meadows extending from Jammu and Kashmir to Arunachal Pradesh. At an altitude between 3700 and 4600, it is also found in Nepal, Bhutan, China and Pakistan.

Religious Belief of *Saussurea obvallata*

The plant is very sacred in the region. It is considered a spiritual flower for Lord Vishnu in the Badrinath temple and Lord Shiva in the Kedarnath shrine. Brahma Kamal is offered as prasada in temples during Nanda Ashtami which falls in September or October. Brahma Kamal is said to have been created by Brahma to help Lord Shiva to place the elephant head on the body of Lord Ganesha, as stated by Hindu mythology. The 'Amruta' flower was dropped. It is also said that in celebration of Lakshmana's survival through Sanjeevani, the Gods rained down the Brahma Kamal from heaven. Consequently, the Brahma Kamal fell to the ground and grown itself in the Valley of Flowers. The local people, along with its religious significance, widely choose the plant for the preparation of traditional Ayurvedic medicines. The rhizomes, leaves and petals are used to treat urinary tract problems, coughs and colds, digestive disorders and bone pain. The rhizomes in particular are antibacterial and are used to treat cuts and wounds.

Ethnobotany uses of *Saussurea obvallata*

A treatment including the roots is used to treat cuts and wounds. In hydrocele, flower bracts boiled in water are used as a stimulant. The flowers are deposited between layers of clothing to keep insects away [14].

Traditional medicine and folk practice of *Saussurea obvallata*

The species continues to play a notable role in the treatment of many diseases, old and new, and is widely used in traditional medicine. Various species of *Saussurea* are used in different traditional and folk medical practices in India, China, Tibet, Nepal, Pakistan, Bangladesh and other Asian countries. Past few decades, the Himalayan people of Nepal, Tibet, China and the Indian Himalayas used *S. obvallata* to treat or cure a number of diseases and conditions, cerebral ischemia, including stroke, heart, wounds, and mental disorders; some use it as an antiseptic and to heal cuts, etc. [15-23].

The natives of the upper mountain region of the Greater Himalayas are familiar with various species of *Saussurea*. These are highly valued medicinal plants in Tibetan culture. However, their immense traditional medicinal value is not proven in many aspects of their medicinal efficacy. The entire plant of *S. obvallata* can be used for the management of numerous serious diseases. In folk medicine, it is used as a liver tonic. Its bitter taste also makes it an excellent appetizer suppressant. In Tibetan culture, extracts prepared from *S. obvallata* are popularly used to treat inflamed liver and also help in increasing blood volume. The plant soup is useful in treating different disorders related to the urinary system. Sexually transmitted diseases and some chronic urinary tract diseases are also successfully managed by Brahma Kamal in Himalayan medicine. It is a potent antipyretic [24] and shows the Table No.1.. The whole plant is useful in managing bone pain, intestinal disorders and seasonal cough and cold. It is useful in Ecchymosis and wound owing to its strong antiseptic action. Plegia and cerebrovascular ischemia are managed by Brahma Kamal in folk Amchi medicine[25].

S. gossypiphora plants mentioned in folk Tibetan literature have blood-clotting properties, owing to which its flower is used to stop bleeding after injury. *S. gossypiphora* (Kasturi kamal) also has the power to cure menstrual cramps, rheumatic ailment, pulmonary disorders, skin disorder, and hysteria [26]. *S. simpsoniana* is very useful in managing all kinds of nervous disorders, leucorrhoea, cough and cold and other sexual disorders. It is a very good blood detoxifier. Its root soup effectively treats snake bites and menstrual cramps. *S. obvallata* represents the sacred values of Hinduism, owing to which the Uttarakhand government declared *S. obvallata* as the flower of the flesh [27]. This sacred flower is used for prayers at the famous Hindu shrines of Baba Kedar Nath and Badrinarayan Temple. "Nanda Ashtami" is a popular festival of Uttarakhand, dedicated to "Devi Nanda" for the prosperity of the world. *S. gossypiphoram* is believed to protect us against evil spirits. Its root oil is used to make the world's most expensive perfume and very good hair oil. The basis of *S. simsoniana* is to protect winter clothes from insects[28].

Table No.1. Ethno pharmacological uses of *Saussurea obvallata*

PLANT PARTS	ETHNO PHARMACOLOGICAL	USES DOSAGE FORM	COUNTRY
Whole Plant	<i>It is used in the treatment of paralysis of limbs and cerebral ischemia</i>	-	Tibet
	<i>It is used for the treatment of headache and body pain</i>	<i>The paste prepared from whole plant is applied</i>	India
	<i>It is used to protect woolen clothes from the damages caused by insects</i>	<i>Whole inflorescence</i>	India
	<i>It is used for the treatment of bruises and cuts</i>	<i>The paste prepared from whole plant is applied</i>	India
Roots	<i>It is used as antiseptic and also used for healing cuts and bruises</i>	<i>The paste prepared from root is applied</i>	India
	<i>It is used to cure boils</i>	<i>The paste prepared from root is applied</i>	Pakistan
	<i>It is used to cure leucoderma</i>	<i>The paste prepared from root is applied</i>	India
	<i>It is used to cure fever and cough</i>	-	India
	<i>It is used to cure cardiac disorders</i>	<i>Decoction of roots (200ml) mixed with 2-3 spoons full of the oil of cedrus deoder and applied externally to treat the heart (100ml)</i>	India
	<i>It is used to cure bruises and fractures</i>	<i>Decoction of roots (200ml) mixed with 2-3 spoons full of the oil of cedrus Deoder (100ml)</i>	India
Leaves	<i>It is used to cure boils ,cuts and wounds</i>	<i>Decoction of dried leaves (100ml) mixed with half spoonful of salt and few drops of this ,applied in the infected area (20ml*3days)</i>	India
	<i>It is used to cure bruises and fractures</i>	<i>Decoction of roots (200ml) mixed with 2-3</i>	

		spoons full of the oil of cedrus deoder (100ml)	India
	It is used to cure wounds and cuts	Dried leaves with salt (10gm)and used in infected area	India
Flower	Used to treat boils ,hydrocele and	-	India
Buds	reproductive disorders		
	It is used to cure boils ,cut and bruises	The paste prepared from flower is applied	Pakistan
	It is used to treat bone –ache , intestinal ailments, urinary tract problems and coughs	-	India
	It is used to treat urinary infections in cattle	Raw form	India
	Flower heads are used to cure hydrocele	Flower heads are roasted with ghee and one to two tea spoons (full) are given to patients in the morning for 3-6 days	India
Bracts	It is used to treat cough and respiratory problems	-	India
Seed	It is used to treat mental disorders	The powder of seeds steeped in water overnight then filtered (1 cupful)	India

Phytochemical components of *Saussurea obvallata*

S. obvallata (whole plant) leaves and flower extracts Their phenols, proteins, saponins, steroids, strontium, tannins, terpenoids, alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, sesquiterpenes, lactones, calcium, chromium, copper, ferrous ions, iron, lead, magnesium, minerals, manganese, minerals, zinc [29-38] and shows the **Table No.2.**

Table No.2. Preliminary phytochemical constituents analyses of *Saussurea obvallata*

Extract s	Alkaloids	Phe nol	Tanni ns	Flavonoids	Terbenoids	Glycosides	Proteins	Saponins	Steroids
Chloroform	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
Methanol	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
Ethanol	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-
Distilled water	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+

Positive (+) show the presence of constituents; whenever negative (-) show the absence of constituents in the *Saussurea obvallata*

Antimicrobial activity of *Saussurea obvallata*

Currently, the high risk of infection and resistance to antibiotics has become a persistent and global problem and antibiotics are often used indiscriminately against diseases caused by various microorganisms. Therefore, it is a main task for investigators to continuously monitor an alternative chemical agent against these human pathogens. In this study, four bacterial strains and three fungal strains were used to analyze the antimicrobial activity of *S. obvallata* extracts. *S. obvallata* extracts (20µl of 5 mg/mL) were evaluated against four bacterial strains (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) and three fungal strains (*Candida albicans*, *Candida glabrata*, and *Candida*

tropicalis). The well diffusion method to used and carry out the antimicrobial assay. The zone of inhibition measurements carried out during the investigation revealed that the methanolic and aqueous extracts had moderate antibacterial and antifungal activity against all pathogens. These ranges ranged from 8.30 to 15.90 mm and 8.87 to 20.50 mm, respectively[29].

Khalid et al., [39] reported the antimicrobial activity of *S. lappa* root extract against three Gram-positive and two Gram-negative bacteria. Methanol, hot water and cold water were used for extraction and the range of inhibition zone was found to be 10 to 18 mm for methanolic extract, 8–11 mm for hot water extract and 9–13 mm for cold water extract. Antimicrobial activity of methanolic and chloroform extracts of *S. lappa* against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, *p. vulgaris*, *S. aureus*, *C. albicans*, *A. niger* was reported by Tara & Zuhra [40]. Both extracts of *S. lappa* revealed significant activity against all bacterial strains, but some fungal strains showed low partial inhibition. Antimicrobial activity of *Saussurea lappa* (roots) Negi et al.,[41] Samples were collected from four different parts of Uttarakhand and methanol was used for extraction. Negi et al.,[41] Six bacterial strains (*S. typhimurium*, *E. coli*, *C. freundii*, *P. vulgaris*, *E. faecalis* and *S. aureus*) were tested. The ZOI were 6-8mm for *E. coli*, 5-10mm for *C. freundii*, 5-8mm for *E. faecalis* and 6-10mm for *S. aureus*. The extract of *S. lappa* exhibited superior activity against these four bacterial strains compared to the known standard used. Two bacterial strains, *Proteus vulgaris* and *S. typhimurium*, showed resistance against the root extract up to 100 mg mL⁻¹ concentrations. Alaagib et al., [42] antibacterial activity of *S. lappa* (black root) extract against five bacterial strains (*B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae*) was also reported.

Antioxidant activity of *Saussurea obvallata*

Two methods (DPPH test and H₂O₂ assay) were used to assess antioxidant activity in vitro; significant variation ($p < 0.05$) and minor variation were noted, respectively. Methanolic and aqueous extracts of flowers showed the highest and lowest percentages of DPPH free radical scavenging activity, whereas aqueous and methanolic extracts of leaves showed intermediate values. In addition, methanolic leaf extract and aqueous leaf extract had the highest and lowest percentages of H₂O₂ free radical scavenging activity, respectively, while aqueous and methanolic extracts of flowers had intermediate values of H₂O₂ free radical scavenging activity[43].

The most vital role of antioxidants is to suppress free radical mediated oxidation by inhibiting the production of free radicals through scavenging activity. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard antioxidant compound for DPPH assay and H₂O₂ scavenging assay. The highest percentage of DPPH scavenging activity ($82.88 \pm 0.48\%$) was recorded in the methanolic extract of flowers, and the lowest ($29.25 \pm 0.86\%$) was in the aqueous extract of flowers of *S. obvallata*. The highest percentage of H₂O₂ scavenging activity ($41.05 \pm 0.46\%$) was in the methanolic leaf extract and the lowest ($39.75 \pm 0.36\%$) was in the extract at a concentration of 1mgmL⁻¹ [44].

Anticancer activity of *Saussurea obvallata*

When *S. obvallata* leaf and flower extracts were tested against MCF-7 breast cancer cell lines, they demonstrated a substantial amount of activity in comparison to a positive control. Mishra et al. (2018). Several plant-based biological components, including paclitaxel (from *Taxus brevifolia*), camptothecin (from *Camptotheca acuminata*), podophyllotoxin (from *Podophyllum emodii*), and vinblastine (from *Catharanthus roseus*), have been developed as sources of anticancer agents[45]. Present scientific efforts have focused on the potential roles of traditional herbal extracts as alternative and complementary medicines for cancer treatment [46-48]. Currently, solid evidence reported by several investigators has suggested different anticancer activities of *S. lappa* extracts both in vitro and in vivo [49-51].

However, the effect of *S. lappa* extract on KB human oral cancer cell growth has not been investigated. As shown in the results, *S. lappa* extract inhibited the growth of KB cells in a dose- and time-dependent

manner. Consequently, in this study, to elucidate the mechanism of cytotoxic activity of *S. lappa* extract on KB human oral cancer cells. Apoptosis is characterized by distinct morphological features and the formation of a ladder of genomic DNA fragments[52]. Results showed the appearance of a DNA ladder in KB cells treated with *S. lappa* extract. This result suggested that *S. lappa* extract could induce apoptosis in KB cells. Consequently, results performed a series of experiments to identify the mechanism of *S. lappa* extract-induced apoptosis in KB cells. Effects of *S. lappa* extract on Bcl-2 family proteins. In a previous study, the cytotoxic effects of *S. lappa* extract on AGS gastric cancer cells were reported to be downregulated by Bax, Bad, and Bcl-2 and Bcl-xl[53]. Therefore, the present findings should facilitate further work to investigate the beneficial effects of *S. ovalata* extract in cancer treatment and elucidate its mechanism of action.

Conclusion

In the present paper, *Saussurea obvallata* is discussed in terms of its traditional uses, phytochemistry, pharmacology and botanical studies. *S. obvallata* is one of the most significant species in the Himalayan regions and according to a review of the literature, is used in many traditional medicines. In addition, there are few researches available for this species in terms of chemical characterization, pharmacological evaluation of antioxidant, antimicrobial and anticancer activity.

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